

Droop-Control-Aided State Estimation and False Data Detection in Active Distribution Systems

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an enhanced state estimation (SE) method for active distribution systems (DSs) is presented. The advancement of the proposed method lies in the integration of the local control logic of the distributed renewable energy sources, i.e., the droop control, into the mathematical formulation of the SE optimization problem. The proposed method is evaluated in comparison with the conventional weighted least squares SE method, both as a stand-alone state estimator and under false data injection cyberattacks. Simulations on two real-world medium-voltage DSs demonstrate the improved performance of the proposed method in terms of estimation accuracy and system observability, as well as its superiority against both random and sophisticated false data injection attacks.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

AWGN	Additive white Gaussian noise
BESS	Battery energy storage system
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
DRES	Distributed renewable energy source
DS	Distribution system
DSO	Distribution system operator
DSSE	Distribution system state estimation
FDD&R	False data detection and removal
GAMS	General algebraic modeling system
LNR	Largest normalized residual
MC	Monte Carlo
MINLP	Mixed integer nonlinear programming
MV	Medium voltage
NLP	Nonlinear programming
SE	State estimation
SHGME	Schweppe-Huber generalized M-estimator
WLS	Weighted least squares

Mathematical symbols

Sets

\mathcal{N}	Network buses.
\mathcal{N}_s	Slack bus.
\mathcal{N}_{zero}	Zero-injection buses.
\mathcal{N}_{inj}	Injection buses.
\mathcal{N}_{DRES}	Buses hosting DRESs.
\mathcal{M}_P	Buses with active power measurements.
\mathcal{M}_Q	Buses with reactive power measurements.
\mathcal{M}_V	Buses with voltage measurements.
\mathcal{M}	Total measurement set.
\mathcal{M}_P^a	Buses with active power measurements accessed by the adversary.
\mathcal{M}_Q^a	Buses with reactive power measurements accessed by the adversary.
\mathcal{M}_V^a	Buses with voltage measurements accessed by the adversary.

Parameters of the DSO

N	Number of buses excluding the slack bus.
m	Number of measurements used for the DSSE.
M	Total number of available measurements, including the virtual measurements of zero-injection buses.
M_{min}	Minimum number of measurements required for a DS to be observable.
\hat{P}_i	Active power measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
\hat{Q}_i	Reactive power measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
\hat{V}_i	Voltage measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
σ_{P_i}	Standard deviation of active power measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.

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σ_{Q_i}	Standard deviation of reactive power measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
σ_{V_i}	Standard deviation of voltage measurement at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
\mathbf{z}	Total measurement vector, including virtual measurements of zero-injection buses
\mathbf{H}	Jacobian matrix of the DS.
$\mathbf{H}_{\text{droop}}$	Matrix representing the droop control equations.
\mathbf{H}_{aug}	Augmented Jacobian matrix of the DS, including the droop control equations.
\mathbf{R}	Measurement covariance matrix.
$\mathbf{\Omega}, \mathbf{\Omega}_{ii}$	Residual covariance matrix and residual covariance of the i -th measurement with $i \in \mathcal{M}$, respectively.
c	Detection threshold.
c_b	Detection threshold applying the Bonferroni correction.
CI	Confidence interval for false data detection.
G_{ij}	Conductance matrix element for buses $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$.
B_{ij}	Susceptance matrix element for buses $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$.

Parameters of the adversary

G_{ij}^a	Conductance matrix element for buses $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$, as assumed by the adversary.
B_{ij}^a	Susceptance matrix element for buses $i, j \in \mathcal{N}$, as assumed by the adversary.
\mathbf{A}	Fictitious DS operating point introduced by the adversary.
p	Maximum absolute percentage deviation of the admittance matrix parameters.

Variables / unknown quantities of the DSO

\mathbf{x}	State vector.
\mathbf{e}	Measurement noise vector.
V_i	Voltage estimate at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
$V_{x,i}, V_{y,i}$	Real and imaginary part of voltage estimate at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, respectively.
P_i	Active power estimate at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
Q_i	Reactive power estimate at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
\mathbf{r}, r_i	Residual vector and residual of the i -th measurement with $i \in \mathcal{M}$, respectively.
$r_{n,i}$	Normalized residual of the i -th measurement, $i \in \mathcal{M}$.
r_{\max}	Largest normalized residual.
i_{\max}	Measurement corresponding to the normalized residual, with $i \in \mathcal{M}$.

Variables of the adversary

V_i^a	Falsified voltage value at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
$V_{x,i}^a, V_{y,i}^a$	Real and imaginary part of falsified voltage value at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, respectively.
P_i^a	Falsified active power value at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.
Q_i^a	Falsified reactive power value at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$.

Functions

$h()$	Nonlinear function correlating measured and state quantities.
$g_V()$	Piecewise linear function of the droop control $Q(V)$ curve.
$f()$	Function of the falsified values representing an emergency condition for the DS.

Metrics

APE_{X_i}	Absolute percentage error between the estimate X_i and the true value X_i^{true} , where X denotes any of $P, Q, \text{ or } V$.
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1. Introduction

Monitoring and control are the main cornerstones of the smart grid paradigm, facilitating the integration of distributed renewable energy sources (DRESSs) toward a green and sustainable electricity grid [1]. Focusing on the former, the robustness of monitoring schemes can be enhanced by employing state estimation (SE) techniques, which traditionally serve to remove measurement noise and bad data from the measurement dataset. Moreover, in the context of the highly digitized and thus vulnerable smart grids, SE serves as the backbone of false data detection and removal (FDD&R) frameworks, enabling the identification of deliberately injected false data in the event of cyberattacks [2].

In the literature, several distribution system state estimation (DSSE) solutions have been proposed [3, 4], which can be roughly classified into two main categories: machine learning methods and robust optimization methods. Regarding the first category, machine learning techniques are trained on a set of historically available measurements or SE results. More specifically, an unrolled spatiotemporal graph convolutional network is proposed in [5] to incorporate the spatiotemporal correlations of the measurements into the SE process. A similar approach is presented in [6], in which, however, the DS topology is also introduced as a trainable parameter. In [7], the authors propose a Bayesian DSSE technique enhanced with deep learning, designed for DSs with limited measurement availability. To avoid the excessive computational burden in the training process that is posed by the lack of knowledge related to the DS configuration, as well as to further increase the accuracy of the DSSE, physics-informed solutions have recently been proposed [8–10]. In [8] and [9], an enhanced neural network and a temporal convolutional network are introduced, respectively, integrating the DS admittance matrix into the training process. This idea has been further extended in [10], considering the topology changes of the DS in the analysis. Moreover, in [11], a framework for exploiting DSSE results by learning-based methodologies is proposed. Finally, in [12], a graph neural network approach is used for multiarea DSSE.

In the second approach, robust optimization techniques are applied to solve the DSSE problem, focusing on improving the computational performance and the estimation accuracy. In particular, the authors in [13] use the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to solve the DSSE problem. Moreover, the well-established backward-forward sweep method is used in [14] to prevent ill-conditioning issues and ensure robust convergence along with a low computational burden. In [15], the conventional weighted least squares (WLS) method is replaced by two robust regression estimators to improve the estimation accuracy. A two-time-scale approach is presented in [16] to handle different types of measurements used in the DSSE. In [17, 18], gradient-based DSSE approaches are examined, aiming to achieve faster convergence and better handling of measurement asynchronicity, respectively. Furthermore, to overcome the increased computational complexity caused by the inherent nonlinearities, linearization techniques based on the Taylor series and the linear programming contractor are used in [19] and [20], respectively. Finally, in [21], an enhanced initialization process is proposed, using a neural network to accelerate the convergence and improve the stability and accuracy of the robust optimization algorithm.

As a common drawback, none of the above studies leverages the local control logic of DRESs, e.g., droop control, for enhancing the DSSE. To elaborate, as DRESs proliferate, such control schemes are widely deployed for voltage regulation purposes, while, in terms of monitoring, they can provide additional insights into the DSSE. Nonetheless, despite the growing interest in examining DSSE under increased DRES penetration [22], only a few works have addressed the droop control aspect, specifically [23–25], albeit focusing solely on microgrid applications and not DSs.

More specifically, in [23], the authors propose a distributed dynamic SE strategy tailored for microgrids dominated by battery energy storage systems (BESSs). Nevertheless, the developed method is not suitable for DSs, as it does not incorporate power flow equations and only considers BESS-related dynamics. In [24, 25], $P(f)$ and $Q(V)$ droop control schemes are included into the SE to consider the active and reactive power sharing among the DRESs within a microgrid. Nevertheless, a simplified approach is adopted, in which the droop control schemes are implemented by simple, linear curves. In contrast, in DS applications, piecewise linear droop curves are assigned to DRESs, to cover a wider range of operating conditions, as imposed by the IEEE Standard 1547 [26]. In addition, both works focus solely on assessing the SE accuracy, without evaluating the impact of the developed methods on system observability. Furthermore, the work of [24] lacks a comprehensive validation under false data injection cyberattacks, while the study of [25] does not consider such cyberattacks at all. Finally, although the authors in [27] state that droop control schemes are included in the DSSE, the analysis therein lacks a thorough investigation in terms of both numerical results and discussion.

Based on the above, the scope of this paper is to address this gap by proposing an enhanced DSSE method for active DSs with high DRES penetration. The contribution lies in the incorporation of the local control logic of the DRESs, i.e., droop control, in the mathematical formulation of the DSSE problem, as well as in the evaluation of the proposed DSSE method under different performance criteria.

More specifically, the proposed enhanced DSSE method is comparatively evaluated against the conventional WLS solution in two stages. The first stage, covered in the previous study of the authors [28], involves a stand-alone comparison of the two DSSE methods, in terms of estimation accuracy and system observability. The second stage, which constitutes the additional contribution of the present study, incorporates both DSSE methods into an FDD&R framework, and evaluates their performance against false data injection attacks. The study considers both random and sophisticated false data injection attacks, assuming varying degrees of measurement accessibility and DS parameter knowledge by the adversary. The two validation stages are carried out via simulations on two distinct real-world medium-voltage (MV) DSs in Greece, one exclusively active DS and one mixed DS with both loads and DRESs.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the mathematical background of the proposed DSSE method, as well as the FDD&R framework into which it is incorporated. Subsequently, Section 3 performs the stand-alone evaluation of the proposed DSSE method, in terms of estimation accuracy and system observability. The performance of the proposed DSSE method against false data injection attacks is assessed in Section 4. In Section 5, the execution time of the method is discussed. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by highlighting the main findings and discussing directions for future research.

2. Proposed Method

2.1. Proposed Enhanced DSSE method

In a power system with $N+1$ buses and M available measurements, the formulation of any SE problem can be encapsulated by (1):

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{e}. \quad (1)$$

Here, \mathbf{x} is the $(2N+1) \times 1$ vector of system states, \mathbf{z} denotes the $M \times 1$ vector of measured quantities, $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ represents the nonlinear set of mathematical functions correlating \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{z} , and \mathbf{e} is the $M \times 1$ vector of measurement errors. If the set of functions $\mathbf{h}(\cdot)$ is approximated by a $M \times (2N+1)$ Jacobian matrix, \mathbf{H} , the linearized SE formulation is derived:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}. \quad (2)$$

The proposed DSSE formulation considers an active DS of $N+1$ buses, comprising the set \mathcal{N} , with subsets \mathcal{M}_P , \mathcal{M}_Q , and \mathcal{M}_V representing the buses with active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude measurements, respectively. The total measurement set is denoted as $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_P \cup$

$\mathcal{M}_Q \cup \mathcal{M}_V$. Moreover, subset $\mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}$ contains the buses with DRES units and subset $\mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}$ represents the zero-injection buses of the system. The singleton set \mathcal{N}_s represents the slack bus of the DS. Variables P_i , Q_i , and V_i denote the estimated values of active power injection, reactive power injection, and voltage magnitude at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, respectively, while parameters \hat{P}_i , \hat{Q}_i , and \hat{V}_i denote the corresponding measured values, if available. The measurements are assumed to be affected by additive errors of zero mean value and variance $\sigma_{P_i}^2$, $\sigma_{Q_i}^2$, and $\sigma_{V_i}^2$, respectively. The measurement variances are stored in the diagonal $M \times M$ matrix \mathbf{R} . Based on the above and assuming that the DRES units operate under a droop control scheme, the proposed DSSE method is mathematically formulated as:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_P} \frac{(P_i - \hat{P}_i)^2}{\sigma_{P_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_Q} \frac{(Q_i - \hat{Q}_i)^2}{\sigma_{Q_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_V} \frac{(V_i - \hat{V}_i)^2}{\sigma_{V_i}^2}. \quad (3)$$

subject to:

$$P_i = V_{x,i} \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j} - B_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j}) + V_{y,i} \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j} + B_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j}), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (4a)$$

$$Q_i = -V_{x,i} \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j} + B_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j}) + V_{y,i} \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j} - B_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j}), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (4b)$$

$$V_i = \sqrt{V_{x,i}^2 + V_{y,i}^2}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (4c)$$

$$V_{y,i} = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_s. \quad (4d)$$

$$P_i = Q_i = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}. \quad (4e)$$

$$Q_i = g_V(V_i), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}. \quad (4f)$$

Eq. (3) is the WLS objective function, while (4a)-(4c) represent the nonlinear power flow equations in rectangular form. To elaborate, $V_{x,i}$ and $V_{y,i}$ are the real and imaginary parts of the voltage phasor, respectively, while G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the real and imaginary parts of DS admittance matrix, respectively. Eq. (4d) equivalently sets the phase angle of the slack bus as the angle reference, ensuring that the DSSE formulation is not underdetermined. Finally, (4e) leverages the knowledge regarding the zero-injection buses of the DS.

Fig. 1. Considered $Q(V)$ characteristic.

Algorithm 1 LNR Test

- 1: Run the DSSE to compute the estimated state vector \mathbf{x}^* .
 - 2: Calculate measurement residuals: $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{z} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}^*)$.
 - 3: Compute the covariance matrix of the residuals: $\mathbf{\Omega} = \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T$.
 - 4: Compute normalized residuals: $r_{n,i} = \frac{|r_i|}{\sqrt{\Omega_{ii}}}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{M}$.
 - 5: Identify the largest normalized residual: $r_{\max} = \max\{r_{n,i}\}$, $i \in \mathcal{M}$
 $i_{\max} = \arg \max\{r_{n,i}\}$, $i \in \mathcal{M}$.
 - 6: **while** $r_{\max} \geq c$ **do**
 - 7: Remove measurement i_{\max} from the set \mathcal{M} .
 - 8: Repeat steps 1–5.
 - 9: **end while**
 - 10: Process terminates, all false data have been removed.
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The advancement compared to the conventional DSSE is introduced by considering the local control logic of the DRES units. In this study, the $Q(V)$ droop is considered, without loss of generality. This is reflected in the inclusion of (4f), where function $g_V(V_i)$ expresses the piecewise linear $Q(V)$ droop characteristic of the DRES units, as recommended in [26] and illustrated in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1, positive/negative reactive power values indicate injection/absorption, respectively, while per unit (p.u.) values refer to the rated power of each DRES. The piecewise form of Fig. 1 is mathematically represented by introducing binary variables in (4f). Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the proposed mathematical formulation of (3)-(4f) can be appropriately modified if DRESs operate under $P(V)$ or $\cos\phi(V)$ droop control schemes. In such cases, (4f) would be replaced by analogous functions $P_i = g_P(V_i)$ or $\cos\phi_i = g_{\cos\phi}(V_i)$, emulating piecewise linear relations between the corresponding quantities at DRES buses.

2.2. False Data Detection and Removal Framework

In order to enable a fair comparison between the conventional and proposed DSSE methods in the context of false data injection attacks, both methods are integrated into a well-established FDD&R framework. Specifically, the largest normalized residual (LNR) test is applied iteratively, as detailed in [29] and presented in Algorithm 1, to detect and remove false data from the measurement dataset. As

Fig. 2. System under study for the analysis of Section 3.

 Table 1
Line Characteristics

Lines	R (Ω/km)	X (Ω/km)
1-2	2.81	3.11
2-3, 6-7, 6-9, 9-10, 9-12, 12-15, 17-18, 21-24, 21-22, 26-27, 29-30, 32-33, 35-36, 38-39, 41-42, 44-47	0.576	0.4
2-5	0.83	1.06
5-6	0.33	0.23
12-13	0.12	0.08
5-17, 26-29, 29-32, 32-35, 35-38, 38-41, 41-44, 44-45	0.21	0.33
17-20	0.167	1.06
20-21	0.323	0.22
20-26	0.85	1.32

explained in Algorithm 1, the LNR test identifies the measurement corresponding to the LNR, that is, the measurement exhibiting the largest normalized deviation from its estimated value. This measurement is considered the most likely to be a false datum. If the LNR is higher than a predefined threshold c , the corresponding measurement is deemed false and removed from the dataset. The procedure is repeated until the LNR falls below c , indicating that all false data have been removed.

3. Performance in State Estimation

Here, the proposed and conventional DSSE methods are compared in terms of accuracy and observability. The optimization problems of both DSSE methods are formulated and solved on the General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS). The IPOPT and the DICOPT solvers are employed for solving the conventional and the proposed DSSE problem, respectively.

3.1. System Under Study

For this validation stage, the examined system is an exclusively active, real-world MV DS in Greece. The DS comprises 49 buses, among which 16 host a DRES unit

 Table 2
Transformer Characteristics

Transformer	x_k (%)	r_k (%)	S_r (MVA)
0-1	15.7	0.14	20
3-4, 10-11, 15-16, 18-19, 24-25, 22-23, 33-34, 36-37	5.92	1	1
47-48, 45-46	5.92	1	0.8
27-28, 39-40, 42-43	5.87	1.2	0.5
7-8, 13-14, 30-31	5.87	1.2	0.4

 Table 3
DRES Rated Power

$i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}$	Rated power (MVA)
8	0.37
14, 31	0.41
28, 40, 43	0.52
46	0.76
48	0.83
4	0.9
34	0.97
11, 16, 19, 23, 25, 37	1.04

($\mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}$) and 32 are zero-injection buses ($\mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}$), as illustrated in Fig. 2. The 16 DRES buses and the slack bus (Bus 0) comprise the set of injection buses (\mathcal{N}_{inj}). The nominal voltage of the DS is 20 kV, while the DRESs are connected at the level of 0.4 kV. The voltage level of the upstream system is 150 kV. The characteristics of the lines and the transformers are reported in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The DRES rated power is listed in Table 3. All DRESs operate under the $Q(V)$ droop curve of Fig. 1.

3.2. Impact on Estimation Accuracy

The accuracy of the proposed and conventional methods is compared under realistic noise conditions. Specifically, standard deviations of $\sigma_{P_i}=0.012$ p.u., $\sigma_{Q_i}=0.015$ p.u., and

$\sigma_{V_i}=0.01$ p.u. are assumed. These values correspond to the maximum percentage errors in active power, reactive power, and voltage measurements, considering Class 2 meters for active power and voltage, and Class 3 meters for reactive power, with a 95% confidence interval [30–32].

For the considered values of σ_{P_i} , σ_{Q_i} , and σ_{V_i} , 100 Monte Carlo (MC) scenarios are examined, emulating discrete instances of measurement errors on the same operating instance of the DS. In all scenarios, \hat{P}_i , \hat{Q}_i , and \hat{V}_i measurements are assumed to be available at all DRES buses and the slack bus (Bus 0). In each MC scenario, the measurements are assumed to be synchronous and independently affected by additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and a standard deviation of σ_{P_i} , σ_{Q_i} , or σ_{V_i} , depending on the measurement type. It is noteworthy that this is a commonly adopted assumption [29] and represents the most favorable noise condition, under which the WLS estimator is equivalent to the maximum likelihood estimator; thereby enabling a fair comparison between the two DSSE methods.

For each estimated quantity, X_i , the accuracy of the DSSE is evaluated through the absolute percentage error, APE_{X_i} , calculated in (5).

$$APE_{X_i}(\%) = \frac{|X_i - X_i^{\text{true}}|}{X_i^{\text{true}}} \cdot 100\%, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (5)$$

To elaborate, in (5), X_i could represent either P_i , Q_i , or V_i , depending on the estimated quantity, while X_i^{true} denotes the true value of this quantity.

The $APE_{X_i}(\%)$ values concerning the DRES buses, for an indicative MC case, are presented in Table 4. Focusing on the conventional method, the $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ values are consistently at least five times higher than the corresponding $APE_{P_i}(\%)$ values, and approximately two orders of magnitude higher than the corresponding $APE_{V_i}(\%)$ values. The higher $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ values relative to $APE_{P_i}(\%)$ are attributed to the higher σ_{Q_i} value compared to σ_{P_i} . Regarding voltage, beyond the lower standard deviation σ_{V_i} , the much lower $APE_{V_i}(\%)$ values are also explained by the inherently lower variability of voltage as a physical quantity of the DS, and its lower sensitivity to active and reactive power variations. This lower sensitivity is reflected in the $\frac{dV}{dP}$ and $\frac{dV}{dQ}$ sensitivity factors. More specifically, these sensitivity factors have been calculated using the DIGSILENT Powerfactory software and their maximum values across all DS buses are 0.0255 p.u./p.u. and 0.18 p.u./p.u., respectively.

Concerning the effect of the proposed method, as shown in Table 4, the proposed method reduces the $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ by up to 99.8 % (Bus 23) and the APE_{V_i} by up to 98.3 % (Bus 19). In terms of the $APE_{P_i}(\%)$, a slight improvement in the DSSE accuracy of up to 4.7% (Bus 4) is observed.

The overall improvement of the DSSE accuracy, as evaluated by means of the 100 MC simulations, is illustrated in Fig. 3. More specifically, Fig. 3 depicts the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the $APE_{X_i}(\%)$, as computed for all buses and MC cases, for the estimates of active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude. As previously explained, the values of $APE_{P_i}(\%)$, $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$, and

Table 4
Comparison of $APE_{X_i}(\%)$, $i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}$

i	Conventional method			Proposed method		
	P_i	Q_i	V_i	P_i	Q_i	V_i
4	0.42	8.69	0.015	0.4	1.04	0.0028
8	3.53	23.05	0.187	3.43	0.78	0.0243
11	0.46	3.06	0.021	0.45	0.28	0.0032
14	1.82	10.3	0.092	1.78	0.74	0.0036
16	0.52	4.24	0.042	0.5	0.08	0.0077
19	1.44	8.65	0.078	1.4	0.32	0.0013
23	0.75	5.76	0.057	0.73	0.01	0.0092
25	0.3	1.91	0.009	0.3	0.2	0.0046
28	0.25	1.28	0.004	0.24	0.21	0.0038
31	1.57	7.61	0.096	1.53	0.24	0.0154
34	1.3	7.78	0.065	1.26	0.31	0.0015
37	1.13	8.99	0.062	1.1	0.45	0.0011
40	3.73	18.91	0.228	3.61	0.75	0.0268
43	4.9	24.83	0.297	4.76	0.99	0.0333
46	1.05	5.91	0.047	1.02	0.26	0.0027
48	0.67	3.79	0.029	0.65	0.19	0.0042

$APE_{V_i}(\%)$ differ by orders of magnitude. For this reason, the x-axis of Fig. 3 is presented on a logarithmic scale, allowing for a clearer comparison among the three quantities. As demonstrated in Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c, the proposed method leads to considerably lower APE_{X_i} values for the reactive power and voltage estimates. The visual confirmation of Fig. 3 regarding the $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ and $APE_{V_i}(\%)$ reduction is supported by the statistical metrics of Table 5. More specifically, Table 5 reports the mean and maximum values of $APE_{X_i}(\%)$ across all MC cases and buses, as well as the standard deviation of their distribution. As observed, the proposed method achieves a similar percentage reduction of the $APE_{Q_i}(\%)$ and $APE_{V_i}(\%)$ of more than 85% across all statistical metrics. This improved DSSE accuracy is mathematically explained by the introduction of (4f). More specifically, additional information on the correlation between voltage and reactive power is exploited, reinforcing the estimation of the corresponding state variables.

Concerning active power, the estimation accuracy is slightly improved, as visually attested by Fig. 3a and confirmed by the results of Table 4 and the metrics of Table 5. This minor improvement in the active power estimation is explained by the absence of an additional set of equations directly involving active power in the proposed method. Moreover, as indicated by the low values of the $\frac{dV}{dP}$ sensitivity factors, the coupling between active power and voltage is weak; thus, the improvement in voltage estimation does not result in a comparable improvement in active power estimation.

Fig. 3. CDFs of the APE for a) active power, b) reactive power, and c) voltage magnitude, for the proposed and the conventional method. The x-axis is in logarithmic scale.

In conclusion, the additional information regarding the droop control scheme, as leveraged by the proposed method, allows for a more accurate estimation of all quantities of interest in a DS, with a particular upgrade in reactive power and voltage estimation. Special emphasis should be given to the enhancement of the reactive power estimation, as the conventional method yields quite important APE_{Q_i} values, as indicated by both Table 4 and Fig. 3b. This poor performance of the conventional method is attributed to the structure of the conventional DSSE method and the deficient accuracy of the reactive power meters, as expressed by the high σ_{Q_i} value. Nonetheless, the proposed method addresses this inherent drawback of the conventional DSSE method and considerably improves the reactive power estimation. This is of significant importance in modern DSs, as DS operators (DSOs) need to reliably monitor the exchange of reactive power by the DRESs, to ensure that each DRES operates according to the expected droop curve and that voltage regulation is carried out as planned. Notably, the operation of DRESs under a $Q(V)$ droop is an ancillary service, whose fair remuneration requires reliable monitoring.

3.3. Impact on System Observability

Here, a theoretical analysis is conducted to evaluate the impact of the proposed method on improving system observability. The impact of the proposed method on the

observability of the examined DS is quantified by the minimum number of measurements required. Specifically, the observability of a system is expressed by the column rank of matrix \mathbf{H} ; if \mathbf{H} has full column rank, the system is observable. Thus, for any system of $N+1$ buses, the minimum required number of measurements is $M_{\min} = 2N + 1$, as a lower number of measurements renders \mathbf{H} rank-deficient.

Theoretically, an unobservable system requires additional measurements to become observable. From a mathematical perspective, the incorporation of additional measurements corresponds to an increase in the number of rows of vector \mathbf{z} and matrix \mathbf{H} . Alternatively, the implementation of the proposed method achieves the same effect, thanks to the inclusion of (4f), and without the need for additional measurements. Specifically, under the proposed method, the system Jacobian matrix becomes $\mathbf{H}_{\text{aug}} = [\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H}_{\text{droop}}^T]^T$, with \mathbf{H} denoting the system Jacobian matrix corresponding to the conventional method and $\mathbf{H}_{\text{droop}}$ denoting the matrix that represents the additional droop control equations.

For the examined DS, $N = 48$, and hence, $M_{\min} = 97$. Indeed, the availability of \hat{P}_i and \hat{Q}_i for any set of 48 buses, out of the 49 in total, and of \hat{V}_i for the substation (Bus 0), ensures observability. In practical terms, by leveraging the reliable information regarding the zero-injection buses and reasonably assuming the availability of the \hat{P}_i , \hat{Q}_i , and \hat{V}_i measurements at the substation, the system becomes observable if power meters are installed at least at any 15 out of the 16 DRES buses, measuring active and reactive power. Therefore, the conventional method requires 30 measurements, which along with the three substation measurements and the 64 virtual measurements for the zero-injection buses, constitute the 97 required measurements.

Conversely, the proposed method augments \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{H} , as each available voltage measurement at a DRES bus introduces an additional equation. Consequently, under the proposed method, the installation of voltage sensors at any 15 out of the 16 DRES buses suffices for the observability of the system. Therefore, the minimum required number of measurements is 15. To elaborate, in conjunction with the three substation measurements and the 64 virtual measurements of the zero-injection buses, the 15 voltage measurements would increase the total number of measurements, and thus the rank of \mathbf{H} , to 82, which is deficient. Nevertheless, the rank of the actual Jacobian matrix, \mathbf{H}_{aug} , is 97, thanks to the inclusion of (4f), hence mathematically validating the possession of sufficient information to perform the DSSE. The minimum observability requirements under the conventional and the proposed method are summarized in Table 6.

Therefore, the proposed method can ensure the observability of the system with a simpler type of metering device, i.e., voltage sensors instead of active/reactive power meters, and fewer measurements, i.e., 15 instead of 30. This translates into significantly lower expenditure and data load. Specifically, voltage sensors are considerably cheaper than active/reactive power meters, as the latter also imply the existence of current sensors. Moreover, reducing the required number of measurements by half results in lighter

Table 5

 Statistical Metrics of APE_{X_i} (%) and Percentage Improvement Introduced by the Proposed Method

X_i	Conventional method			Proposed method			Percentage Improvement (%)		
	mean (%)	max (%)	std (%)	mean (%)	max (%)	std (%)	mean (%)	max (%)	std (%)
P_i	1.5	11.8	1.5	1.47	11.5	1.45	3.9	2.8	2.7
Q_i	10.5	112.9	11.3	0.46	4.6	0.5	95.6	95.9	95.6
V_i	0.041	0.62	0.05	0.0058	0.07	0.0051	85.9	88.7	90.5

Table 6

Minimum observability requirements

Method	Measurement Number	Meter Type
Conventional	30	Power meters
Proposed	15	Voltage sensors

data traffic and reduced data storage demands. Thus, the method addresses one of the main issues that decelerate the practical application of SE in DSs, namely the excessive data handling and data storage requirements, imposed by the size and complexity of DSs.

4. Performance in False Data Detection and Removal

After comparatively evaluating the stand-alone performance of the proposed and the conventional DSSE methods in Section 3, in this section, the methods are compared in terms of FDD&R. To this end, both DSSE methods are incorporated into the FDD&R framework of Section 2.1, specifically in Step 1. The analysis examines both random and sophisticated false data injection attacks.

4.1. System Under Study

For this validation stage, the system under study is a mixed real-world MV DS in Greece, comprising 180 buses (\mathcal{N}), of which 67 host loads, 16 host DRESs ($\mathcal{N}_{\text{DRES}}$), and 96 are zero-injection buses ($\mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}$), as shown in Fig. 4. The 67 load buses and 16 DRES buses, together with Bus 0, which represents the upstream system (slack bus), constitute the set of 84 injection buses (\mathcal{N}_{inj}). The nominal voltage of the DS is 20 kV, while the DRESs are connected at the level of 0.4 kV. The voltage level of the upstream system is 150 kV. For the standard deviations, values of $\sigma_{P_i} = 0.0033$ p.u., $\sigma_{Q_i} = 0.01$ p.u., and $\sigma_{V_i} = 0.0016$ p.u. are considered, corresponding to the actual meter classes of the DS (Class 0.5 S, Class 1, and Class 0.5, for active power, reactive power, and voltage, respectively). The same droop control logic explained in Section 3.1 is applied to all DRESs. The parameters of the DS are available at [33]. It is assumed that active power, reactive power, and voltage measurements are available only for the 84 injection buses of set \mathcal{N}_{inj} , resulting in a total of 252 available measurements.

4.2. Generation of False Data Injection Attacks

4.2.1. Random Attacks

In these attacks, random values within predefined ranges are injected at randomly selected buses of set \mathcal{N}_{inj} . For voltages, values between 0.8 p.u. and 1.2 p.u. are injected. For active and reactive power, the injected values range from 0% to 200% of the actual measured values. These ranges are selected to enhance the plausibility of the manipulated data.

4.2.2. Sophisticated Attacks

To further evaluate the performance of the FDD&R frameworks against more plausible false data, sophisticated false data injection attacks are generated. For these attacks, it is assumed that the adversary is aware of the DS topology, knowing the connections between buses and the locations of zero-injection buses. This knowledge enables the adversary to strategically determine the buses to be attacked and the manipulated data to be injected, solving an optimization problem. The optimization problem aims to generate false data corresponding to a fictitious operating point \mathbf{A} , such that \mathbf{A} represents an emergency condition in the DS, e.g., voltage limit violations at specific buses. Therefore, this fictitious operating point \mathbf{A} aims to compromise the situational awareness of the DSO, potentially triggering unnecessary control actions that could lead to cascading negative effects on the DS operation. Moreover, to achieve stealthiness, the falsified values of the operating point \mathbf{A} should exhibit minimal deviation from the actual measured values. Based on the above, the optimization problem for the derivation of sophisticated false data injection attacks is formulated as:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_p^a} (P_i^a - \hat{P}_i)^2 + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_Q^a} (Q_i^a - \hat{Q}_i)^2 + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_V^a} (V_i^a - \hat{V}_i)^2. \quad (6)$$

subject to:

$$P_i^a = V_{x,i}^a \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij}^a \cdot V_{x,j}^a - B_{ij}^a \cdot V_{y,j}^a) + V_{y,i}^a \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij}^a \cdot V_{y,j}^a + B_{ij}^a \cdot V_{x,j}^a), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (7a)$$

$$Q_i^a = -V_{x,i}^a \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij}^a \cdot V_{y,j}^a + B_{ij}^a \cdot V_{x,j}^a)$$

Fig. 4. System under study for the analysis of Section 4.

$$+ V_{y,i}^a \cdot \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij}^a \cdot V_{x,j}^a - B_{ij}^a \cdot V_{y,j}^a), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (7b)$$

$$V_i^a = \sqrt{(V_{x,i}^a)^2 + (V_{y,i}^a)^2}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (7c)$$

$$V_{y,i}^a = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_s. \quad (7d)$$

$$P_i^a = Q_i^a = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}. \quad (7e)$$

$$f(V_i^a, P_i^a, Q_i^a) \geq \mathbf{A}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (7f)$$

Variables P_i^a , Q_i^a , and V_i^a denote the falsified values, whose aggregate absolute deviation from the actual measured values is minimized in the objective function (6). The sets \mathcal{M}_P^a , \mathcal{M}_Q^a , and \mathcal{M}_V^a are subsets of \mathcal{M}_P , \mathcal{M}_Q , and \mathcal{M}_V , respectively, representing the degree of measurement accessibility for the adversary. Moreover, $G_{ij}^a \neq G_{ij}$ and $B_{ij}^a \neq B_{ij}$

model the inaccuracy and uncertainty in the knowledge of the DS parameters by the adversary. Furthermore, constraint (7f) represents the objective of the attack, with $f(\cdot)$ generally denoting a function of the falsified values. Indicatively, if the objective is to introduce a fictitious overvoltage at Bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, constraint (7f) would be $V_i^a \geq 1.1$ p.u. Finally, it is assumed that the adversary is not aware of the DRES operation under the $Q(V)$ droop control scheme. This assumption is justifiable because the $Q(V)$ droop is a local control scheme, with the droop settings typically configured on-site at the power converters of the DRESs during the commissioning of the DRES plants.

For both SE methods, the performance of the FDD&R framework is evaluated using the *Accuracy* (%), *Precision* (%), *Recall* (%), and *F₁ score* (%) metrics (8a)-(8d). The true and false positives (*TP*, *FP*) and negatives (*TN*, *FN*) are defined based on the measurements detected as false data. More specifically, true positives refer to detected false data that have indeed been falsified by the adversary, whereas false positives refer to detected false data that have not been falsified. In turn, assuming that measurements are affected by AWGN and considering a 99.7% confidence interval, a measurement is labeled as false if the deviation between the manipulated value and the original, unaffected value exceeds

Fig. 5. (a) Voltage, (b) active power, (c) reactive power measurement profiles for a random and a sophisticated attack at Bus 103 under 25% measurement accessibility.

the standard deviation of the measurement by more than ± 3 times. Regarding the detection threshold at Step 6 of Algorithm 1, the widely used value of $c = 3$ is selected [29, 34, 35], corresponding to a 99.7% confidence interval.

Finally, similar to the DSSE optimization problems, the optimization problem of (6)–(7) for the derivation of sophisticated attacks is formulated and solved using GAMS.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}. \quad (8a)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \quad (8b)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (8c)$$

$$F_1 \text{ score} = \frac{2 \cdot Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}. \quad (8d)$$

4.3. Validation against Attacks with Varying Measurement Accessibility

In this section, attacks with varying degrees of measurement accessibility are examined. More specifically, the

measurement accessibility percentage of the adversary is varied from 0% to 100% in increments of 5%. For the cases of 0% accessibility, the measurements at only one bus are manipulated. Regarding the random attacks, for each examined percentage, 20 attacks are generated, each one targeting different, independently and randomly selected buses. Regarding the sophisticated attacks, for each examined percentage, 20 different target buses are independently and randomly selected; subsequently, a sophisticated attack is generated for each selected target bus. Therefore, a total of 420 random attacks and 420 sophisticated attacks are examined in this section. For all sophisticated attacks, the fictitious operating point \mathbf{A} corresponds to an overvoltage at the target bus. In order to evaluate the impact of measurement accessibility, for these attacks, it is assumed that the adversary has perfectly accurate knowledge of the DS admittance parameters, i.e., that $G_{ij}^a = G_{ij}$ and $B_{ij}^a = B_{ij}$.

Indicative cases of a random and a sophisticated attack with 25% measurement accessibility are presented in Fig. 5, with both attacks targeting Bus 103. As observed in Fig. 5, the random attack falsifies a total of 50 measurements (21 voltage, 22 active power, and 7 reactive power measurements), whereas the sophisticated attack falsifies only 11 measurements (4 voltage, 3 active power, and 3 reactive power measurements). This significantly lower number of affected measurements by the sophisticated attack is a result of the stealthy design. More specifically, for the given measurement accessibility percentage, sophisticated attacks aim to introduce an emergency condition in the DS—in this case, an overvoltage at Bus 103—by generating falsified values that exhibit minimal deviation with respect to the actual measurements and adhere as closely as possible to the physical laws of the DS. In this context, the optimization problem of (6)–(7) may choose not to manipulate some of the available measurements if their falsification would increase the overall deviation in (6). Conversely, in random attacks, the adversary affects all available measurements with randomly injected values.

The performance metrics for the FDD&R framework under the conventional and the proposed DSSE methods are summarized in Table 7 and Table 8, for the random and the sophisticated attacks, respectively. The tables report the mean value of each metric, computed over the 20 attack cases for each measurement accessibility percentage. As presented in Table 7, the proposed method achieves improved performance for random attacks, as evidenced by the higher values across all performance metrics. More specifically, for low measurement accessibility percentages, i.e., between 0% and 10%, the two methods exhibit equivalent performance, effectively identifying and removing all manipulated data. However, as expected, the performance of both methods deteriorates with increasing measurement accessibility percentage, that is, with an increasing number of false data in the measurement dataset.

The superior performance of the proposed method is more evident for the sophisticated attacks, as attested by the results of Table 8. As shown, the proposed method

Table 7
Random Attacks with Varying Measurement Accessibility: Mean Performance Metrics per Percentage

Measurement accessibility (%)	Conventional method				Proposed method			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score
0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
5	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
10	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
15	99.9	100.0	82.2	90.2	99.9	100.0	88.1	93.6
20	99.9	100.0	65.0	78.8	99.9	100.0	70.0	82.4
25	99.5	94.0	53.0	66.0	99.6	95.0	68.0	79.3
30	91.9	88.1	40.7	55.6	92.0	71.5	60.0	65.1
35	90.7	88.6	39.8	54.8	91.5	75.0	60.1	66.6
40	89.6	88.8	41.3	56.2	90.9	77.7	61.3	68.3
45	88.7	91.2	41.6	57.0	88.9	75.7	57.5	65.2
50	87.3	90.0	41.5	56.7	88.5	78.4	59.2	67.4
55	86.1	90.3	41.7	57.0	87.1	77.1	58.7	66.6
60	84.8	90.1	41.1	56.4	85.9	78.6	56.6	65.8
65	83.6	90.0	41.7	56.9	84.7	78.4	57.3	66.1
70	82.9	90.8	42.0	57.3	83.6	78.0	56.0	65.1
75	81.3	90.1	41.0	56.3	82.3	78.0	55.4	64.7
80	79.8	88.4	40.7	55.7	81.8	80.5	55.0	65.3
85	78.5	89.2	40.6	55.8	79.6	79.3	52.9	63.4
90	77.3	89.2	40.3	55.4	78.3	80.0	50.9	62.2
95	75.6	89.3	38.7	54.0	77.9	82.4	51.5	63.3
100	75.2	92.1	38.5	54.3	77.5	84.2	50.8	63.4

Table 8
Sophisticated Attacks with Varying Measurement Accessibility: Mean Performance Metrics per Percentage

Measurement accessibility (%)	Conventional method				Proposed method			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score
0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
5	99.9	94.0	94.0	94.0	99.9	95.7	98.0	96.7
10	100.0	100.0	98.3	99.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
15	99.9	100.0	80.8	86.1	99.9	100.0	86.7	89.8
20	99.8	100.0	63.5	72.5	99.8	100.0	69.5	78.2
25	99.3	93.0	51.8	60.7	99.4	92.0	66.6	72.7
30	99.2	91.0	35.9	46.5	99.3	95.0	52.2	61.9
35	98.6	94.7	25.2	34.5	98.8	96.2	33.5	44.8
40	97.9	87.8	17.6	27.4	98.1	91.5	33.8	45.4
45	96.9	75.9	15.2	23.1	97.4	87.0	27.3	38.0
50	97.1	88.4	10.2	17.6	97.5	93.9	23.2	35.1
55	94.8	69.1	10.1	15.5	95.5	79.0	26.5	36.2
60	94.4	78.7	8.3	13.1	95.1	85.3	22.3	32.1
65	92.0	68.5	9.6	16.0	92.9	79.4	21.5	32.3
70	90.0	73.8	7.6	12.9	90.8	79.8	17.6	27.4
75	86.0	55.9	8.8	14.5	87.8	78.3	18.1	28.7
80	84.4	59.2	8.1	13.6	86.2	78.8	17.0	27.3
85	81.3	54.0	7.8	13.2	82.7	69.3	16.0	25.6
90	75.0	73.4	12.7	21.2	77.0	80.3	21.8	33.4
95	69.3	65.2	12.7	21.1	72.4	75.5	22.2	34.1
100	54.0	–	0.0	–	65.5	95.5	26.3	41.2

consistently outperforms the conventional method across all performance indices. Moreover, the comparative improvement in FDD&R introduced by the proposed method becomes more pronounced as measurement accessibility increases. Specifically, the performance of the conventional

method deteriorates significantly, exposing its vulnerability to sophisticated attacks. Notably, under 100% measurement accessibility, the conventional method fails to detect any false data ($TP = FP = 0$), and thus to even identify the occurrence of any of the 20 attacks, resulting in a

Fig. 6. Voltage profiles under a sophisticated attack: (a) Original and manipulated measurements; (b) Estimates under the conventional method and identified false data; (c) Estimates under the proposed method and identified false data.

complete loss of situational awareness regarding the state of the DS. In contrast, the proposed method successfully identifies the attacks, detecting and removing a substantial number of false data. Thus, incorporating the local droop-control logic of the DRES units in the proposed enhanced DSSE method acts as an advantage for the DSO, improving situational awareness, counteracting the full measurement accessibility and accurate parameter knowledge of adversary, and preventing their attempt to introduce the fictitious operating point **A**. Furthermore, as discussed in Section 3.3, the enhanced mathematical formulation of the proposed method enables the removal of multiple false measurements without compromising system observability. Conversely, for conventional DSSE methods, the removal of such a high number of false measurements would not be possible, as it would result in a loss of observability.

Finally, to better visualize the effect of incorporating the local droop control logic into the proposed DSSE method, an indicative case of a sophisticated attack is elaborated. More specifically, an attack with 30% measurement accessibility is examined, with the measured and estimated voltage and reactive power profiles illustrated in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively. The profiles involve the buses of set \mathcal{N}_{inj} . As depicted in Fig. 6a and Fig. 7a, the attack results in two false data for both voltage and reactive power, at

Fig. 7. Reactive power profiles under a sophisticated attack: (a) Original and manipulated measurements; (b) Estimates under the conventional method and identified false data; (c) Estimates under the proposed method and identified false data. Due to the large magnitude difference, the reactive power at Bus 0 (substation) is depicted separately for better clarity.

Bus 175 and Bus 177, while a fictitious overvoltage at Bus 177 is introduced by the adversary. The remaining measurements are not affected by the attack, either because they are inaccessible to the adversary or because the attack optimization problem decides not to alter them in order to minimize deviations in (6). Under the conventional method, as depicted in Fig. 6b, the estimates are such that allow the identification of the two false data in the voltage measurement profile. Nevertheless, apart from these true positives, the estimates of the conventional method result in two false positives, i.e., in two unaffected voltage measurements to be mistakenly identified as false data. Moreover, as depicted in Fig. 6b, the deviation between the estimates and the original measurements is large, indicating that despite the correct identification of the two false data at Bus 175 and Bus 177, the situational awareness is compromised. Regarding reactive power, as observed in Fig. 7b, the performance is further deteriorated, as the conventional method fails to identify the two actual false data and instead considers the reactive power measurement at Bus 0 to be manipulated (false positive). In contrast, as visualized in Fig. 6c and Fig. 7c, under the proposed method, the two false data are correctly identified for both voltage and reactive power (true positives). Furthermore, the estimates better match the

Table 9
Sophisticated Attacks with Varying Parameter Deviation: Mean Performance Metrics per Percentage

Maximum absolute parameter deviation (%)	Conventional method				Proposed method			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1 score
0	54.5	–	0.0	–	65.1	96.2	24.2	38.7
5	54.3	–	0.0	–	64.8	95.1	24.0	38.4
10	54.8	–	0.0	–	65.1	94.9	24.1	38.3
15	54.3	–	0.0	–	64.9	95.9	24.3	38.7
20	53.1	–	0.0	–	63.3	95.6	22.8	36.5
25	53.5	–	0.0	–	64.5	96.3	24.6	39.2
30	54.5	–	0.0	–	64.2	94.5	22.7	36.6
35	53.7	–	0.0	–	64.4	97.7	23.6	37.8
40	53.9	–	0.1	–	64.5	95.7	24.2	38.5
45	53.4	–	0.0	–	63.5	94.0	23.0	36.8
50	53.6	–	0.0	–	64.3	97.0	23.8	38.0
55	53.9	–	0.4	–	64.1	95.6	23.2	37.3
60	55.5	–	0.9	–	65.0	96.0	23.0	36.9
65	54.4	–	0.8	–	64.6	97.4	23.6	37.8
70	54.5	–	0.8	–	64.7	96.8	24.0	38.2
75	54.4	–	1.0	–	63.2	96.9	20.7	33.9
80	54.8	–	2.3	–	64.6	95.6	24.1	38.4
85	54.4	–	0.9	–	63.2	94.9	21.1	34.3
90	54.2	–	0.7	–	64.1	96.6	22.7	36.6
95	55.5	–	3.1	–	64.7	96.6	23.9	38.1
100	54.9	–	1.8	–	63.6	95.2	21.8	35.1

original, unaffected measurements, restoring the awareness and the monitoring capability of the DSO.

4.4. Validation against Attacks with Varying Admittance Parameter Deviation

In this section, attacks with varying degrees of admittance parameter deviation are examined. Specifically, the maximum absolute percentage deviation, p (%), between the actual DS parameters, G_{ij} and B_{ij} , and those assumed by the adversary, G_{ij}^a and B_{ij}^a , is varied from 100% to 0% in decrements of 5%. For each examined percentage p , the G_{ij}^a and B_{ij}^a parameters are independently assigned random values within the ranges of (9), following a uniform distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(1 - \frac{p}{100}\right) \cdot G_{ij} &\leq G_{ij}^a \leq \left(1 + \frac{p}{100}\right) \cdot G_{ij}, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{N} \\ \left(1 - \frac{p}{100}\right) \cdot B_{ij} &\leq B_{ij}^a \leq \left(1 + \frac{p}{100}\right) \cdot B_{ij}, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{N}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

For each examined percentage p , 20 different target buses are independently and randomly selected; subsequently, a sophisticated attack is generated for each selected target bus. Thus, a total of 420 sophisticated attacks are examined. For all attacks, the fictitious operating point \mathbf{A} corresponds to an overvoltage at the target bus. To evaluate the impact of parameter deviation, full measurement accessibility is assumed for the adversary in all examined attacks. The assumption of 100% measurement accessibility enables generating highly challenging attack cases for the DSO, allowing for a safe comparative evaluation of the two DSSE methods

The mean performance metrics for the FDD&R framework under the conventional and the proposed DSSE methods are presented in Table 9. As observed, due to full measurement accessibility, the attacker can freely manipulate the entire measurement set and thereby launch stealthy attacks that evade detection by the conventional method. Specifically, under the conventional method, situational awareness is completely compromised, as even in the scenarios with large parameter deviations, there exist attack cases for which no false data are detected ($TP = FP = 0$). These results showcase the vulnerability of conventional DSSE methods and FDD&R frameworks when subjected to attacks that exploit full measurement access and topology knowledge, as adversaries can launch stealthy attacks even under substantial errors in their admittance parameter assumptions.

In contrast, the proposed enhanced DSSE method successfully identifies all attacks, detecting and removing a significant number of false data. The relatively lower metrics compared to those of Table 7 and Table 8 are attributed to the extremely high proportion of falsified measurements, as nearly the entire dataset is manipulated under the assumption of 100% measurement accessibility. Moreover, for the same reason, the results of Table 9 exhibit reduced sensitivity to variations in the parameter deviation percentage p , with similar mean *Precision*, *Recall*, and F_1 score values reported across all examined percentages. More specifically, due to the high proportion of manipulated measurements, the number of false positives remains low across all examined parameter deviation percentages, resulting in consistently high *Precision* values. Although increased parameter deviations

Table 10
Impact of Detection Threshold for Sophisticated Attacks with Varying Measurement Accessibility

10% measurement accessibility	Conventional method				Proposed method			
	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score
Base case	1	0	0	100.0	1	0	0	100.0
Case 1	1	2	0	50	1	2	0	50
Case 2	1	0	0	100.0	1	0	0	100.0
35% measurement accessibility	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score
Base case	2	0	13	23.5	5	0	10	50.0
Case 1	4	4	11	34.8	5	4	10	41.6
Case 2	2	0	13	23.5	3	0	12	33.3
100% measurement accessibility	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score
Base case	0	0	248	-	67	1	181	42.4
Case 1	0	0	248	-	69	1	179	43.4
Case 2	0	0	248	-	62	1	186	39.9

reduce the compatibility of falsified measurements with the physical laws of the DS, the almost complete manipulation of the dataset distorts the DSSE process, yielding a consistently high number of false negatives and, thus, a similarly low *Recall* across all examined deviation percentages.

In conclusion, the examined scenarios of this section represent extreme cases of false data injection attacks with nearly complete measurement dataset manipulation. In such cases, the performance metrics of (8) are of limited diagnostic value, as the situational awareness and monitoring capability of the DS are inevitably lost. Instead, the primary objective is to identify the presence of the attack itself—a goal achieved by the proposed method in all examined cases, in contrast to the conventional method.

4.5. Impact of Detection Threshold

In this section, a sensitivity analysis with respect to the value of the threshold c is performed. The following cases are considered:

- Base case: Using $c = 3$, similarly to the analyses of Section 4.3 and Section 4.4. This detection threshold corresponds to a 99.7% confidence interval.
- Case 1: Using $c = 1.96$, corresponding to a lower confidence interval of 95%.
- Case 2: Considering a 99.7% confidence interval and applying the Bonferroni correction to take into account the number of the measurements involved in the SE [36]. The adjusted threshold is calculated as:

$$c_b = \Phi^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{CI}{2 \cdot m} \right). \quad (10)$$

where c_b denotes the Bonferroni-based threshold, CI (%) is the desired confidence interval, and m is the number of measurements used for the SE. Finally, $\Phi^{-1}()$ denotes the inverse cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution. Provided that $m=252$ (active power, reactive power, and voltage

measurements for the 84 injection buses) for the DS of Fig. 4, the initial value of c_b is 4.4. In the case of multiple identified false data, the c_b value is readjusted at each iteration of Algorithm 1, as measurements identified as false are removed and m is thereby iteratively decreased.

Three indicative scenarios are considered, specifically sophisticated attacks targeting Bus 79 with 10%, 35%, and 100% measurement accessibility. The corresponding results are presented in Table 10. As observed, no clear dependence exists between the F_1 score and the employed threshold. To elaborate, for the scenario of 10% measurement accessibility, using the lower threshold of $c = 1.96$ results in two false positive detections, thereby reducing the F_1 score for both examined methods. Conversely, for 100% measurement accessibility and when applying the proposed method, this lower threshold allows for the detection of two additional truly manipulated measurements, increasing the F_1 score. In contrast, for the same scenario, the Bonferroni correction yields a higher threshold that prevents the detection of five truly manipulated measurements compared to the base case, thus reducing the F_1 score. Furthermore, for 35% measurement accessibility and when applying the proposed method, the base case of $c = 3$ achieves the best performance, as the threshold of Case 1 results in false positives, while the threshold of Case 2 fails to detect two true positives.

In conclusion, the detection threshold can affect the FDD&R performance for both DSSE methods. As expected, lower thresholds result in a higher number of measurements identified as false, which may include both additional true positives and false positives. Therefore, the effect of the threshold value on the F_1 score is stochastic. As a result, the widely used value of $c = 3$ appears to be the most reliable and universally efficient choice. In any case, this recommendation is not binding, and DSOs can perform statistical analyses to determine the most suitable threshold value for their DSs.

Overall, the most important observation is that the proposed DSSE method outperforms the conventional technique under any examined threshold and for all examined

Table 11
Comparison between the Proposed Method and the Robust SHGME

Measurement accessibility (%)	SHGME				Proposed method			
	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score	TP	FP	FN	F_1 score
10%	1	0	0	100.0	1	0	0	100.0
35%	4	0	11	42.1	1	2	0	50
100%	0	0	0	-	67	1	181	42.4

attack scenarios, indicating that its superior performance is independent of the threshold.

4.6. Comparison with Alternative Methods

In this section, the proposed method is compared against a robust DSSE technique. Moreover, its performance is discussed relative to machine learning solutions.

First, the proposed method is compared against the Schweppe-Huber generalized M-estimator (SHGME) [29]. The comparison involves the three attack scenarios of Section 4.5. The detection threshold is set to $c = 3$, while the characteristic parameter of the SHGME is set to 1.5 [37]. The results are presented in Table 11.

By comparing Table 10 and Table 11 for the attack scenario of 35% measurement accessibility, it is observed that the SHGME outperforms the conventional WLS method for all examined thresholds. For the scenario of 100% measurement accessibility, similarly to the conventional method, the SHGME fails to detect the presence of false data. Nevertheless, as shown in Table 11, the proposed method exhibits superior FDD&R performance across all examined attack scenarios compared to the SHGME.

Regarding machine learning techniques, the relative advantage of the proposed method from a qualitative perspective is its deterministic and straightforward formulation, as well as its direct applicability, since it does not involve parameter tuning or training stages. Moreover, the proposed method can be applied within the framework of physics-informed machine learning solutions, in order to provide additional operating insights and outperform conventional machine learning methods that do not incorporate the underlying physical relations of the DS. For instance, the proposed DSSE method can be applied in conjunction with machine learning techniques [9], as follows: first, the proposed DSSE method is used to extract the system states; subsequently, a machine learning solution is trained on the extracted states to further refine the estimation.

5. Discussion on Execution Time

As demonstrated by the analysis of Section 3, the proposed enhanced DSSE method outperforms the conventional WLS DSSE method in terms of both estimation accuracy and system observability. Moreover, this superior performance renders the proposed method a more reliable tool for detecting and removing manipulated measurements under false data injection cyberattacks, as analyzed in Section 4. The tradeoff for this superior performance is the higher

execution time of the proposed method, owing to its more complex mathematical formulation. Specifically, the conventional method of (3)-(4e) corresponds to a nonlinear programming (NLP) optimization problem. Nonetheless, due to the piecewise linear form of the $Q(V)$ droop curve in Fig. 1, the proposed DSSE of (3)-(4f) corresponds to a mixed-integer NLP (MINLP) problem. On average, the execution time of the conventional method is around 0.008 s for the smaller DS of Fig. 2 and 0.013 s for the larger DS of Fig. 4. Regarding the proposed DSSE, the MINLP formulation increases the execution time to up to 0.9 s for the mixed DS. Thus, the proposed method requires a considerably longer execution time compared to the conventional method. Nevertheless, this execution time remains low, enabling the use of the proposed method in practical DSSE applications. For a further comparison, the execution time of the SHGME tested in Section 4.6 is found to reach up to 15 s.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, an enhanced version of the conventional WLS DSSE method is introduced. The proposed method exploits the new operational paradigm of DRES, which often operate under a $Q(V)$ droop control scheme, to achieve improved accuracy and observability.

The performance of the method is tested on two real-world, active MV DSs located in Greece. First, the proposed method is comparatively evaluated against the conventional SE formulation by means of MC simulations that emulate realistic conditions of AWGN in DSs. The simulation results and the analysis demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed method in terms of improving estimation accuracy, as well as maintaining DS observability under reduced measurement conditions.

Secondly, a parametric analysis is conducted on a mixed real-world MV DS to evaluate the performance of the proposed method toward the identification of random and sophisticated false data injection attacks. In all the examined cases, the proposed method outperforms the conventional DSSE formulation in terms of identifying false data. Thanks to its relative advantages, the proposed method could facilitate the application of DSSE, allowing for the reliable monitoring and efficient identification of false data injection attacks in modern, active DSs.

The main limitation of the proposed method is its increased execution time, which could hinder its use in DSSE applications for very large-scale DSs with multiple DRESs, or in applications that require very low execution times.

Future research should focus on testing the method under more challenging conditions of measurement errors, including different types of noise, as well as asynchronous measurements. Furthermore, the method should be evaluated both in comparison with and in combination with machine learning techniques. Finally, to reduce the execution time, the problem of relaxing and convexifying the proposed MINLP formulation should be explored.

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